

1 **A monocyte-derived macrophage model of HIV-1 infection.**

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6 HIV-1 infection is cell type-dependent. We used next generation sequencing and advanced cell culture
7 systems for unbiased study and description of HIV-1 infection in human cells using a monocyte-derived
8 macrophage *in vitro* model of HIV-1 infection. Infection in the system produced a transcriptome readout
9 consistent with productive infection marked by activation of *Ifi441*.

10 Citations

11 1. Cota, M., Mengozzi, M., Vicenzi, E., Panina-Bordignon, P., Sinigaglia, F., Transidico, P., Sozzani,
12 S., Mantovani, A. and Poli, G., 2000. Selective inhibition of HIV replication in primary macrophages but not
13 T lymphocytes by macrophage-derived chemokine. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences,
14 97(16), pp.9162-9167.

15 GSE180350.
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